

Challenges of Nursing Professional Development Among Nurses at Dinajpur Medical College Hospital, Dinajpur

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ABSTRACT

Background: Professional development is essential for nurses to maintain skills, deliver quality care, and adapt to healthcare changes. In Bangladesh, nurses often face barriers to continuing professional development (CPD), affecting career growth and service quality.

Objective: The study aim to explore the challenges of nursing professional development among nurses at Dinajpur Medical College Hospital, Dinajpur.

Materials and Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study explored the challenges of nursing professional development among 103 purposively selected nurses at Dinajpur Medical College Hospital, Dinajpur. Data were collected through face to face interview using a semi-structured questionnaire.

Results: The most number of respondents were diploma-qualified (55.34%), and mid-career with 5–11 years experiences, yet few held leadership roles, the majority of participants demonstrated good to very good communication skills almost 94.18%. The most significant challenge was limited promotion opportunities followed by lack of in-service training (4.54%) and poor coordination between doctors and nurses (4.52%). Heavy workload, insufficient administrative support, workplace discrimination, and restricted access to higher education and digital resources were also reported. Social factors, including negative public perception of nursing and family responsibilities, further hindered development. The findings highlight systemic, institutional, and cultural barriers limiting nurse's professional growth.

Conclusion: Professional development in Bangladesh remains underutilized and poorly supported. Policy reforms, digital learning access, and public awareness initiatives are crucial to creating a supportive environment. Improving continuing professional development opportunities is vital for building a competent, motivated nursing workforce and ensuring better patient outcomes in Bangladesh.

KEYWORDS: Nurse, Nursing, Challenges, Professional Development, Continuing Professional Development (CPD).

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INTRODUCTION

Nursing professional development (NPD) is a continuous and systematic process that enhances nurses' knowledge, skills, and competencies to ensure high-quality patient care and effective clinical outcomes. Globally, the healthcare sector is becoming increasingly complex due to technological

advancement, rising patient expectations, and the growing burden of chronic diseases (World Health Organization [WHO], 2020). As healthcare systems worldwide confront increasing complexity driven by

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demographic shifts, technological advancements, and rising patient acuity continuous professional development has become essential for improving patient safety and care quality (Institute of Medicine [IOM], 2011). NPD supports lifelong learning, enhances critical thinking, fosters leadership, and equips nurses with the capacity to respond to emerging health challenges (American Nurses Credentialing Center [ANCC], 2020). In such a dynamic environment, nurses must engage in ongoing professional development to maintain competency and deliver safe and evidence-based care (American Nurses Association [ANA], 2021). Professional development activities may include in-service training, workshops, continuing education, clinical mentorship, and participation in professional organizations. In low- and middle-income countries like Bangladesh, the importance of NPD is even more critical due to shortages of skilled nurses, limited resources, and high patient-to-nurse ratios (Begum et al., 2019). Despite global recognition of its importance, nurses in many low- and middle-income countries face substantial barriers to accessing professional development opportunities. These challenges include limited institutional support, inadequate staffing, resource shortages, and insufficient structured training programs (Larsen et al., 2022). Ongoing efforts by the government and national nursing authorities to strengthen the nursing workforce, challenges remain in ensuring consistent professional growth opportunities for nurses (Directorate General of Nursing and Midwifery [DGNM], 2022). Barriers such as inadequate institutional support, lack of training facilities, insufficient staffing, and limited access to continuing education impede nurses' ability to engage in professional development activities (Hossain & Mistry, 2021).

In Bangladesh, the nursing profession has been undergoing gradual reform; however, disparities in training access and workplace support persist, particularly in public hospitals where workloads remain high and infrastructure is limited (Ahmed et al., 2021). Dinajpur Medical College Hospital (DMCH), a major tertiary facility in northern Bangladesh, mirrors many of these challenges faced globally and regionally. Nurses often encounter difficulty attending training due to heavy caseloads, lack of clinical supervision, minimal incentives, and limited opportunities for professional advancement. These factors collectively hinder their professional growth and compromise the overall quality of patient care (Islam & Scott, 2023).

Therefore, exploring the **challenges of nursing professional development among nurses at Dinajpur Medical College Hospital** is crucial for identifying gaps and recommending interventions to strengthen nursing capacity. This study aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by highlighting context-specific barriers and suggesting evidence-based improvements for professional development in Bangladesh's healthcare system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design: This study was a descriptive type of cross-sectional study to explore the challenges of nursing professional development among nurses.

Study place: This study was conducted at Dinajpur Medical College Hospital, Dinajpur.

Study population: Study population was 525 nurse who working at Dinajpur Medical College Hospital, Dinajpur, Bangladesh.

Sampling technique and Sample size: Purposive sampling technique was used to recruit eligible subject and our sample size was 103 nurses.

Duration of study: Duration of this study was July 2024 to December 2024.

Data collection instruments: A semi-structured questionnaire was developed by the researcher based on objectives and variables by literature review. The questionnaire was divided into 2 sections. These were-

- Demographic section – to describe the participant background.
- Closed-ended questions (Likert scale) – to explore the challenges of nursing professional development by 21 questions.

All questionnaire measured by 5-point Likert scale. 5-point Likert Scale which indicates “Strongly Disagree” for score 1, “Disagree” for score 2, “Neutral” for score 3, “Agree” for score 4 and “Strongly Agree” for score 5.

Inclusion criteria of sample

- Participants must be formally registered/licensed nurse & also employed at Dinajpur Medical College Hospital, Dinajpur, Bangladesh.
- Nurses must have a minimum of five years of clinical experience.
- Willingness to participate and to voluntarily share their experiences or information.

Exclusion criteria

- Nurses who are involve in nursing education sectors.
- Unwillingness to participate in this study.

Data collection procedures

Data was collected after obtaining permission from the hospital authority. The written and verbal consent was taken from each respondent after explaining the nature and purpose of the study prior to data collection. The researcher was collected data by face to face interview, using one questionnaire for each respondent. The researcher distributed the questionnaire among 103 respondents and allotted 30 minutes to answer those questionnaires, after 30 minutes the researcher collected the questionnaire from the respondents. For data collection ethical issues were considered of the participants. The respondent was informed by the researcher that they have the right to quit this anytime they want and also strict confidentiality was maintained.

Data analysis procedures: After completion of data collection to maintain consistency data were checked & edited and analyzed by using computer software.

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Ethical implications

Ethical approval of research was taken from ethical research review committee of Dinajpur Nursing College, Dinajpur which was permitted by Rajshahi Medical University. Then researcher request for permission from the director of the hospital with a written application. After getting permission

researcher went to data collection from the respondents. Researcher explained about the purposes of research to the respondents and gathered their data with both verbal & written consent. Researcher ensures privacy & confidentiality, their identities and sensitive information was kept confidential. The participants were respected as they have right to participate or withdraw from the research anytime without having any coercion.

RESULTS

1. Demographic Information of participants (n=103)

Age group (in years)	Frequency (f)	Percentage
26 – 32 years	42	40.78%
33 – 39 years	36	44.66%
40 – 46 years	14	13.59%
47 – 53 years	8	7.77%
54 - 60 years	3	2.91%
Mean age =35.79 years		
Educational qualification		
Diploma in Nursing	57	55.34%
B.Sc in Nursing	29	28.16%
MPH/MSN	17	16.50%
Current Designation		
Staff Nurse	04	3.88%
Senior Staff Nurse	96	93.20%
Nursing Supervisor	03	2.91%
Job Experience (in years)		
5 – 11	64	62.14%
12 – 18	21	20.39%
19 – 25	12	11.65%
26 - 32	6	5.83%
Total	103	100%

Table 1 show out of 103 participants, maximum age group was 44.66% (36) were 33 – 39 years, and the mean age was 35.79 years. The majority of the participants 55.34% (57) qualification was Diploma in Nursing, 28.16% (29) B.Sc in Nursing & 16.50% (17) were qualified MPH/MSN. According to designation, 96 nurses (93.20%) hold the position of Senior Staff Nurse. A small number of participants, only 04 nurses (3.88%) are working as Staff

Nurses. Additionally, just 03 participants (2.91%) are in supervisory roles as Nursing Supervisors, reflecting a very small proportion of respondents in managerial positions. Among the 103 participants, majority 64 individuals (62.14%), have between 5 - 11 years of job experience, indicating that most of the nursing workforce in this study falls within the moderately experienced group.

2. Challenges of Professional Development among participants (n=103)

Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)

SL. No.	Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD
		(5)	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)
		f (%)	f (%)	f (%)	f (%)	f (%)
01	Lack of knowledge about professional development.	24 (23.30)	61 (59.22)	13 (12.62)	04 (3.89)	01 (0.97)

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02	Lack of in-service training opportunities limits my professional development.	62 (60.19)	35 (33.98)	06 (5.83)	00	00
03	Heavy workload prevents me from participating in development programs.	53 (51.46)	42 (40.78)	05 (4.85)	03 (2.91)	00
04	There is limited support from hospital administration for professional development.	51 (49.51)	43 (41.75)	07 (6.80)	02 (1.94)	00
05	Financial limitations discourage me from attending further training or workshops.	28 (27.18)	55 (53.40)	12 (11.65)	08 (7.78)	00
06	Workplace discrimination is a challenge to nursing professional development.	55 (53.40)	38 (36.89)	08 (7.78)	02 (1.94)	00
07	Presence of multiple types of nursing courses in Bangladesh creates equality at joining grade & work.	40 (38.83)	53 (51.46)	09 (8.74)	00	01 (0.97)
08	There are limited promotion opportunities for nurses that hinder professional development.	63 (61.170)	40 (38.83)	00	00	00
09	Poor communication between staff and management affects professional development.	30 (29.13)	60 (58.25)	13 (12.62)	02 (1.94)	00
10	Lack of access to learning resources hinders my professional growth.	30 (29.13)	55 (53.40)	13 (12.62)	05 (4.85)	00
11	Professional development is not prioritized in hospital.	38 (36.89)	50 (48.54)	15 (14.56)	00	00
12	There are limited opportunities for nurses to pursue higher education and research.	35 (33.98)	55 (53.40)	10 (9.71)	03 (2.91)	00
13	Lack of personal motivation often hinders nursing professional development.	30 (29.13)	55 (53.40)	10 (9.71)	05 (4.85)	03 (2.19)
14	Lacking of regular performance appraisals for nurses.	38 (36.89)	53 (51.46)	09 (8.74)	03 (2.91)	00
15	Personal and family responsibilities affect my ability to engage in professional development.	29 (18.16)	53 (51.46)	13 (12.62)	08 (7.78)	00
16	Social perception toward the nursing profession hinders professional growth.	53 (51.46)	34 (33.01)	11 (10.68)	05 (4.85)	00
17	There is no clear career development plan or guideline for nurses in the hospital.	34 (33.01)	54 (52.43)	12 (11.65)	03 (2.91)	00
18	Lack of coordination between doctors and nurses affects professional advancement.	60 (58.25)	37 (35.92)	06 (5.83)	00	00

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19	Opportunities for leadership development among nurses are limited.	40 (38.83)	52 (50.49)	06 (5.83)	03 (2.91)	02 (1.94)
20	There is limited access to digital tools and online resources for improving nursing skills.	36 (34.95)	55 (53.40)	07 (6.80)	03 (2.91)	02 (1.94)
21	Gets jealous of someone else's improvement and, in turn, hampers their professional growth	40 (38.83)	51 (49.51)	09 (8.74)	03 (2.91)	00

Table 2 highlights the various challenges faced by nurses in their professional development, based on responses from 103 participants using a 5-point Likert scale. This result indicated that most of the participants agreed or strongly agreed with the listed challenges. The most significant challenge was the limited promotion opportunities, suggesting that lack of career advancement is a major barrier to professional growth. This was followed by the lack of in-service training opportunities and lack of coordination between doctors and nurses, both of which strongly affected nurses' ability to develop professionally.

Other major issues include heavy workload, limited support from hospital administration and workplace discrimination. These findings indicate systemic and organizational challenges that restrict nurses from engaging in development activities. Participants also expressed concern over limited access to digital tools, poor communication between staff and management and lack of clear career development. Social and personal factors such as family responsibilities and lack of personal motivation also appeared to be barriers, though to a slightly lesser degree.

Overall, the responses suggest that nurses are highly aware of the barriers to their professional development, particularly in relation to institutional support, training opportunities, and systemic structures. These findings underline the urgent need for administrative reforms and targeted support systems to promote continuous professional growth among nurses.

DISCUSSION

The demographic data suggest that while the nursing workforce is relatively experienced, female-dominated, and largely diploma-trained, there is limited upward mobility and leadership access. These factors likely intersect with the institutional and systemic barriers discussed in the broader findings and further emphasize the need for targeted reforms in continuing professional development accessibility, promotion policies, and leadership training in the nursing sector.

The most prominent barrier identified was the lack of promotion opportunities, with a mean score of 4.61 and a standard deviation of 0.49. A remarkable 100% of respondents either strongly agreed or agreed that they were not receiving appropriate promotions. This reflects a deep-rooted issue in career advancement systems within the Bangladeshi nursing sector. Sultana (2024) highlighted

similar stagnation among 12 nurses who had not promoted about 91.67% despite their qualifications and years of service, and Khatri R et al. (2021) found that in Nepal, many nurses remained in the same position for over a decade due to the absence of clear promotion guidelines. Such lack of progression not only demotivates staff but also discourages them from engaging in professional development.

The second major challenge reported was the absence of in-service training opportunities. Approximately 94% of the participants noted that they had limited or no access to structured continuing professional development programs. In-service training is fundamental to maintaining up-to-date clinical competencies. This problem is echoed in the work of Jackson and Manley (2021), who observed that institutional neglect of professional development leads to outdated practices, especially in low-resource settings. Similarly, Munasinghe et al. (2023) in Sri Lanka found that a lack of regular workshops and seminars was a leading cause of professional stagnation among nurses (48%). The absence of CPD also undermines the ability of nurses to respond to evolving health crises and patient care standards.

Another considerable barrier was poor coordination between nurses and doctors, reflected by a mean of 4.52 (SD = 0.60). Over half of the participants strongly agreed that inadequate collaboration with physicians hindered their growth. This finding is supported by Coventry et al. (2015), who argued that hierarchical dynamics in healthcare settings often marginalize nurses, thereby limiting opportunities for interprofessional learning. Khatri et al. (2021) similarly emphasized that weak communication and lack of collaborative culture prevent nurses in South Asia from participating meaningfully in decision-making, which is critical for professional development.

High workload was another recurring concern, with a mean score of 4.41. Nurses reported that excessive patient loads, night duties, and administrative responsibilities left little time for engaging in learning activities. Munasinghe et al. (2023) had find out 72.23% were faces those challenge. Khatri et al. (2021), discussed how chronic understaffing and unrealistic performance expectations discourage nurses from dedicating time to professional advancement. In the current study, participants indicated that even when training was offered, they were unable to attend due to time constraints and lack of coverage.

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Administrative neglect also emerged as a significant issue, with a mean score of 4.39 (SD = 0.69). Respondents indicated that hospital leadership rarely prioritized nurse development, and many reported being excluded from discussions about training or career advancement. According to Khatri et al. (2021), supportive leadership is one of the most crucial enablers of CPD engagement. Without administrative encouragement or financial support, even motivated nurses struggle to pursue further learning.

Discrimination in the workplace was another major concern, reflected by a mean score of 4.42. Participants noted that favoritism, bias based on qualification type (e.g., diploma vs. B.Sc), and gender discrimination were common. Jackson and Manley (2021) observed similar dynamics in other developing countries, where systemic bias often leads to unequal access to CPD and promotion. Sultana (2024) reported that in Bangladesh, many female nurses feel excluded from career-building opportunities due to sociocultural norms and institutional prejudice.

The issue of digital and academic limitations was also highlighted, with mean scores of 4.16 and 4.18 respectively for lack of digital learning tools and absence of higher education opportunities. This supports findings from Munasinghe et al. (2023), who described a digital divide in South Asian nursing, limiting access to online training. Coventry et al. (2015) further emphasized that the inability to engage in academic research or postgraduate study results in under-qualified and under-confident staff, unable to contribute to evidence-based care.

Social perception of nursing in Bangladesh was also found to be a significant challenge. Many participants expressed that the public does not value nursing as a respected profession. This societal undervaluing directly affects self-esteem, motivation, and family support for professional growth. Khatri et al. (2021) and Zamanzadeh et al. (2013) discussed similar cultural perceptions in Nepal and Iran, where nurses face societal pressure to abandon further training or limit their ambitions.

Finally, the lack of leadership development and career planning was another major issue. Only a small percentage of nurses reported having any access to mentorship or planning resources. Jackson and Manley (2021) highlighted the importance of structured leadership programs to empower nurses and facilitate upward mobility. In this study, 93.20% of respondents held the designation of Senior Staff Nurse, while only 2.91% had supervisory roles—indicating a significant lack of vertical mobility in nursing roles at Dinajpur Medical College Hospital, Dinajpur.

The findings from this study clearly illustrate that professional development among nurses is hindered by a combination of structural, interpersonal, and cultural barriers. These results are in strong agreement with existing literature from both local and international contexts. To address these challenges, there is a need for institutional reforms including structured promotion pathways, regular in-service training,

digital access, leadership development, and cultural transformation in the perception of nursing. These changes are essential not only for the well-being of the nursing workforce but also for ensuring quality patient care and long-term healthcare sustainability in Bangladesh.

CONCLUSION

The findings are consistent with regional and global literature, which suggests that nursing professional development is often compromised in low-resource settings due to institutional neglect, policy gaps, and cultural biases. Addressing these challenges requires a coordinated effort from hospital administration, nursing education authorities, and government policymakers. Strategic investment in continuing professional development frameworks, clear promotion pathways, and leadership development programs are essential to empower nurses and improve overall healthcare quality in Bangladesh.

Professional development is not just a personal responsibility but a systemic need that directly affects patient care outcomes. Without targeted reforms, the nursing workforce will remain underutilized, demotivated, and disconnected from the evolving demands of modern healthcare.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to improve nursing professional development at Dinajpur Medical College Hospital, Dinajpur:

- Develop a transparent, merit-based promotion system linked to experience, academic achievement, and performance evaluations to motivate career advancement.
- Recruit adequate nursing staff and implement balanced duty rosters to reduce burnout and free up time for learning and growth.
- Foster communication and collaboration between nurses, doctors, and administrators to build a respectful, team-oriented environment conducive to shared learning.
- Launch campaigns to elevate the public image of nursing as a skilled and essential profession, encouraging family and societal support for further education. Organize structured, ongoing in-service training and workshops to nurses for best outcomes.
- Advocate for national-level nursing development policies that mandate continuing professional development as part of licensing and career progression criteria.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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